

HIRSHFELD SURFACE ANALYSIS OF THE COCRYSTAL BETWEEN CU(II) COMPLEX OF SALICYLIC ACID AND UNCOORDINATED PIRACETAM

**Nazokat N. Yuldasheva¹, Adkhamjon S. Normamatov², Abror Kh. Ruzmetov²,
Aziz B. Ibragimov^{2*}**

¹Khorezm Mamun branch of Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences, Markaz-1, Khiva
220900, Uzbekistan;

²Institute of General and Inorganic Chemistry of Uzbekistan Academy of
Sciences, 100170, Mirzo Ulug'bek str., 77a;

e-mail: aziz_ibragimov@mail.ru

Examining intermolecular interactions in crystals becomes quantitative with Hirshfeld surface analysis. This method reveals how close neighboring atoms are on both the internal (d_i) and external (d_e) surfaces surrounding each point on the Hirshfeld surface. These unique features have proven valuable in understanding the selectivity and specificity of intermolecular forces that influence how molecules pack together.

To calculate short-range contacts within the crystal lattice, Crystal Explorer version 21.5 was employed [1]. This software was also used to analyze the crystal structures Hirshfeld surfaces and generate the corresponding two-dimensional (2D) fingerprint plots [2].

In our research, we investigated the arrangement of one molecule of piracetam positioned between two molecules of a binuclear coordination compound consisting of copper metal and salicylic acid. This arrangement played a role in the overall surface formation to some extent. It is worth noting that the piracetam molecule remained neutral, similar to rare co-crystals. This finding aligns with the observations made by Ruzmetov et al. [3].

To comprehensively capture the interactions within the molecular crystals, we utilized the entire compound molecule for the calculation of the Hirshfeld surface.

The primary objective was to provide a comprehensive representation of the molecular interactions. The Hirshfeld surface of the compound was mapped by calculating the normalized contact distance d_{norm} , and the resulting surface was visualized using indicator colors such as red, white, and blue. The obtained results revealed a range of recorded interactions in molecular crystals, spanning atomic sizes from -0.6259 (indicated by red) to 2.0808 (indicated by blue).

The total Hirshfeld surface area was determined to be 1665.66 Å², with a specific surface area of 1132.36 Å². Notably, the interactions within the molecular crystals prominently involved oxygen atoms as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. The Hirshfeld surface of the cocrystal.

Analysis of the 2D fingerprint plot of the compound's Hirshfeld surface (Fig. 7) reveals the dominance of hydrogen-hydrogen (H•••H) interactions, contributing approximately 47% to the overall surface. Notably, these interactions play a crucial role in crystal packing. Additionally, significant contributions are observed from O•••H/H•••O interactions (24.9%), primarily involving oxygen atoms acting as hydrogen bond acceptors and donors. These interactions further enhance the stability of the crystal structure. Additionally, hydrogen-carbon interactions (H•••C/C•••H) account for 20.5% of the surface formation. Interactions involving carbon atoms (C•••C) and oxygen-carbon contacts (O•••C/C•••O) play a minor role (4.5% and 2.5%, respectively). Interestingly, the fingerprint plot reveals minimal contributions from hydrogen-nitrogen interactions (H•••N/N•••H, 0.6%) and oxygen-oxygen interactions (O•••O, 0.1%).

Literature:

1. Spackman, P. R., Turner, M. J., McKinnon, J. J., Wolff, S. K., Grimwood, D. J., Jayatilaka, D., & Spackman, M. A. (2021). CrystalExplorer: A program for Hirshfeld surface analysis, visualization and quantitative analysis of molecular crystals. *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, 54(3), 1006-1011.
2. Spackman, M. A., & Jayatilaka, D. (2009). Hirshfeld surface analysis. *CrystEngComm*, 11(1), 19-32
3. Ruzmetov, A. K., Ibragimov, A. B., Yakubov, Y. Y., Akitsu, T., Shimonishi, D., Ibragimov, A. B., ... & Hossain, A. M. S. (2023). Synthesis, crystal structure and Hirshfeld surface analysis of binuclear Cu (II) complexes from *o/p*-hydroxybenzoic acid with ethanol and water solution of monoethanolamine. *Polyhedron*, 242, 116491.